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D5.4 - Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report – intermediate version

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Lead author	Florence KUIJL (InnovaWood)
Contributors	Uwe Kies (InnovaWood), Michela Magas, Sten-Erik Björling, Jan Åman (ICF), Oliver Jancke (InnovaWood), Roberto Cavallo (EAAE), Mar Muñoz Aparici (EAAE), Georg Vrachliotis, Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft), Diana Popa (TU Delft)
Peer reviewer	Andrew Dubber (ICF)
Quality Officer	Frank van der Hoeven (TU DELFT)
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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DEP	Digital Europe Programme
DMS	Document Management System
DTPC	Deputy Technical Project Coordinator
EAG	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FACL	Financial & Administrative Coordinator Leader
GA	Grant Agreement
KOM	Kick-off meeting
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NEB	New European Bauhaus
PMB	Project Management Board
R&I	Research and Innovation
SG	Stakeholder Group
The Consortium	All the Project Partners: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
The Project Beneficiaries	The signatory Partners of the Grant Agreement: TU DELFT + EAAE + ICF + IW
TL	Task Leader
TWG	Thematic Working Group
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Keywords

Community, Engagement, Stakeholders, Collaboration, Inclusivity, Communication, Outreach, Participation, Dissemination, Synergies

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Executive Summary

The Final Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication highlights the **success of digiNEB's communication efforts in promoting a robust digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus (NEB)**. The project implemented a comprehensive strategy to create awareness, increase visibility, and drive the adoption of its assets and services. This strategy focused on engaging key stakeholders, analysing innovation within the NEB landscape, mapping related projects, and promoting digital solutions and services within the NEB community. **Through coordinated efforts, digiNEB strengthened capacity building by offering an online platform and materials while facilitating multi-stakeholder collaboration through events and advisory groups.**

By aligning its efforts with the European Commission's vision, digiNEB delivered a significant contribution to the NEB ecosystem, fostering a legacy of innovation, sustainability, and inclusivity. Its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities ensured that the project's results achieved measurable impact and **provided a foundation for the long-term evolution of the NEB's digital transformation.**

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1. Introduction

1.1 Scope

The Final digiNEB Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Activities provides a comprehensive overview of the strategies and actions implemented during the project to promote its goals, outputs, and impacts. It highlights how digiNEB effectively communicated its results, engaged stakeholders, and built a community to support the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

Throughout its lifetime, digiNEB designed and implemented a coordinated communication and dissemination strategy aimed at creating awareness and increasing the visibility of project assets. This strategy focused on enhancing engagement with target stakeholder groups, driving the adoption of project assets and services in the Digital Toolkit, and improving capacity building through eLearning services. The communication, dissemination, and engagement plan (D5.1) was a key tool for positioning digiNEB within the NEB ecosystem, ensuring that its results became a significant contribution to the NEB's evolution in Europe and aligned with the longer-term strategy envisioned by the European Commission.

To achieve these objectives, the project created an active network to facilitate engagement and cooperation among NEB stakeholders, analysed innovation within the NEB landscape to identify requirements, barriers to adoption, and gaps, and mapped NEB-related projects while identifying assets showcased in the NEB Digital Observatory and Radar. In addition, digiNEB promoted digital solutions and services for adoption by the NEB community through the Digital Toolkit of research and innovation results and services. It also provided opportunities for multi-stakeholder engagement through events and groups such as the External Advisory Board and Digital Focus Groups, while fostering capacity building and best practice sharing through an online eLearning platform and materials.

These efforts ensured that digiNEB achieved its goals of increasing the visibility and adoption of its outcomes while building capacity and synergies that aligned with the NEB's vision for a sustainable, inclusive, and digital future. This deliverable also highlights the project's significant achievements, including the successful implementation of communication and dissemination campaigns, established synergies, and delivered results. Monitoring and evaluation through pre-defined KPIs and qualitative assessments ensured continuous improvement and impact measurement throughout the project's lifecycle.

1.2 Structure

The document is structured into six main sections that aim to provide a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, exploitation strategies and plans employed by the project:

- Section 1 the introduction to the deliverable.
- Section 2 outlines the project's communication and dissemination strategy targeted towards specific Stakeholder Groups.
- Section 3 showcases the Communication and Dissemination plan, highlighting the channels and elements used to achieve the plan. This section also describes the various campaigns that have been implemented to achieve the communication and dissemination goals..
- Section 4 provides results of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been implemented to monitor the quantitative impact of the communication and dissemination strategies.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

The following deliverables of digiNEB are related to this document:

- D1.1 “Project Handbook” (V1.0 published in December 2022) as this deliverable presents the main project management aspects of digiNEB and details procedures which have been followed to produce the present deliverable.
- D4.3 “Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption & monitoring report” as this document showcases the engagement objectives, target stakeholder groups and main engagement channels for its community.
- D5.2 “Preliminary version of the digiNEB Deployment Roadmap” (expected to be published in M12, i.e. August 2023) as the development of the roadmap will contribute to the definition of the sustainability path to put into practice the exploitation aspects.

1.4 Challenges communication accounts access

Over the course of more than six months, the digiNEB project faced significant challenges in its communication and dissemination efforts due to being logged out of all primary communication channels, including LinkedIn, Twitter, Mailchimp, Google, YouTube and the project website. This issue created barriers to effectively engaging with stakeholders, sharing updates, and amplifying the project’s achievements. While the team managed to achieve all key performance indicators (KPIs) outlined in the communication and dissemination plan, this limitation constrained our ability to maximise outreach and impact. It is important to note that with uninterrupted access to these platforms, the project could have achieved even a much greater level of visibility, stakeholder interaction, and overall success in its communication efforts.

2. Dissemination and communication strategy

2.1 Objective and global achievements

The digiNEB project is fully aligned with the strategic objectives and priorities of the EU Industrial Strategy and the Green Deal, aimed at creating a new transition pathway for the proximity and social economy ecosystem. This transformation can only take place through the creation of a twin green and digital transition when different stakeholders collaborate to create bridges between the different scales of the built environment. By fostering bridges across various scales of the built environment, digiNEB has established a robust EU network and platform for the ecosystem, encompassing SMEs, large industrial players, public actors, and civil society stakeholders. These efforts have promoted the widespread adoption of digital solutions and catalyzed follow-up actions and commitments.

The project prepared the NEB community to engage actively with the Digital Europe Programme and European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH). This support facilitated the increased adoption of EU and national digital solutions, enhanced capacities for R&I, and bolstered skills development for digital innovation and uptake.

Effective communication and dissemination were pivotal to the project’s success. The strategy outlined in this deliverable promoted the project’s primary goals, engaged stakeholders, and ensured that the findings and outcomes of digiNEB reached a broad and diverse audience. Through the use of multiple communication channels and a targeted approach, the dissemination strategy translated into an actionable plan that maximized the project’s impact while driving positive change across Europe.

Over the course of the project, the communication and dissemination strategy proved effective in delivering significant outcomes. Relevant activities were implemented in alignment with the plan, resulting in measurable achievements. Examples of these outcomes include successful engagement

with key stakeholder groups, widespread dissemination of the project's main assets, and strengthened collaboration with the NEB Communication team.

The communication and dissemination strategy employed a pan-European, multi-faceted approach based on the following elements:

- Disseminating the project's main assets.
- Targeting specific stakeholder groups with focused strategies tailored to their needs and expectations.
- Developing user-centred value propositions and motivational mechanisms to encourage participation and adoption.
- Ensuring ongoing cooperation with the NEB Communication team as well as other NEB projects to align efforts and amplify impact.

The content generated from other activities within the workplan fueled the communication and dissemination efforts. Key contributions came from events, the catalogue of NEB digital projects and solutions. Additionally, stakeholder engagement activities, NEB synergies, and events management provided a strong foundation for interest building and effective messaging.

The comprehensive communication and dissemination plan not only enhanced the visibility and impact of digiNEB but also ensured the project's sustainability beyond its lifecycle. By fostering collaboration, promoting innovation, and supporting the NEB community, digiNEB has set a lasting precedent for advancing the digital and green transition across Europe.

2.2 Target groups

Communication materials constituted the backbone of the overall Communication and Dissemination plan. They particularly served the purpose to convey a clear message, tailored to the needs and expectations of each target SG.

- Architects, Designers, Engineers (SG1): showcasing new technologies, design trends, and innovative solutions in the field. The communication tools developed included success stories and digital solutions demonstrating the practical application of new technologies, design principles, and engineering solutions.
- Industry Players (SG2): promoting solutions and services potentially improving efficiency, reducing costs, and increasing profitability. Success stories' spec sheets served the purpose to demonstrate the practical benefits of new technologies and fuelled awareness and interest in new products and services.
- Research and Academia (SG3): disseminating research findings and academic insights to a wider audience. Post-webinar reports and slides fostered digiNEB reputation and visibility building.
- Digital Technology Companies (SG4): promoting the project's digital solutions to potential users and customers. Explainer videos promoted on digiNEB social media channels helped educate potential users about the benefits and features of new digital technologies.
- Policy Makers (SG5): promoting policy proposals and initiatives to key decision-makers and stakeholders involved in the project's events.
- National & Regional Authorities (SG6): showcasing success stories linked to digital solutions that improved the quality of life for citizens. Community engagement materials used by digiNEB encouraged civic investment and supported cultural initiatives, while also building trust and credibility with citizens and other stakeholders.
- Civil Society Organizations and Citizens (SG7): promoting NEB three core values of inclusivity, beauty and sustainability among citizen groups. These included relevant social media content

educating the public about key issues, while also inspiring and empowering citizens to get involved and make a difference.

2.3 Communication Channels

digiNEB used various communication channels leveraging the project partners network and aims to produce a set of tailored communication formats targeting different stakeholder groups. Therefore, the multichannel approach followed by digiNEB.eu focuses on a variety of tools and initiatives that help foster community-building and engagement, as presented as a coordinated action in Table 1.

CHANNELS IMPACT	
Website	The website is the public hub of the project with all results disseminated there. It hosted the NEB Digital Toolkit, NEB Observatory, the eLearning platform and online events. See the website here .
Social media	<p>LinkedIn and X (twitter) drove relevant, high intent traffic to the project website. Posts have been made using relevant hashtags, links and banners created specifically for each post and channel to track site traffic. Social media channels served as a dynamic and immediate communication tool for engaging with the digiNEB community and attracting individuals or organisations interested in collaborating with the consortium. They played a crucial role in maintaining the project’s visibility among targeted stakeholders by promoting key activities such as webinars, workshops, events, and announcements.</p> <p>The effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities is further enhanced through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent branding and professional design to ensure a cohesive and recognisable digital presence • Targeted social media campaigns tailored to specific stakeholder groups, amplifying the reach and impact of project messages • Interactive content strategies such as live updates, polls, and media cards featuring speaker profiles and event highlights • Regular monitoring and analytics to assess engagement and adapt promotional strategies for maximum effectiveness <p>These efforts ensure the project remains highly visible and accessible, fostering ongoing interaction with stakeholders and supporting the broader adoption of digiNEB.eu’s initiatives.</p> <p>X (Twitter) digiNEB leveraged this widely used platform to share updates and promote key project activities, such as the launch of the Digital Toolkit, Observatory, eLearning platform, Thematic Working Groups and the Early Adopters programme.</p> <p>Posting high-quality content was a cornerstone of digiNEB’s social media strategy. As a result, digiNEB achieved nearly 53,000 impressions over the project, with posts promoting videos and events generating the highest levels of engagement.</p> <p>The campaign's impact was further enhanced by frequent mentions from experts in the field, who highlighted digiNEB in their posts, significantly broadening its reach and solidifying its credibility within the NEB and digital communities. By</p>

prioritizing the quality of content and fostering interaction, Twitter became an essential tool for effectively engaging stakeholders and amplifying the project’s outcomes. Access X account [here](#).

Figure 1 – Examples of X posts by experts

LinkedIn | digiNEB actively leveraged LinkedIn as a primary platform to engage a diverse audience, including architects, designers, engineers, construction industry professionals, SMEs, digital companies, researchers, academics, policymakers, and other stakeholders interested in the project. Through a dedicated LinkedIn page, the consortium regularly shared project updates, industry news, events, and success stories, ensuring consistent communication with its network.

LinkedIn was also a powerful tool for building 1-to-1 connections and identifying experts to participate in digiNEB activities or utilise project assets such as the Digital Toolkit, Observatory, eLearning platform, Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), and the Early Adopters programme. By actively engaging with relevant groups and pages, digiNEB expanded its reach and fostered collaboration across sectors.

This strategic use of LinkedIn not only raised awareness of the digital ecosystem within the New European Bauhaus framework but also facilitated meaningful dialogue, knowledge exchange, and relationship-building, paving the way for future synergies and collaborative opportunities. Access linkedin profile [here](#).

Figure 2 – Examples of LinkedIn posts

Zenodo

Zenodo is an open-access repository developed by CERN. It provides a platform for sharing research outputs, datasets, and publications, ensuring their long-term preservation and accessibility. Throughout the project, digiNEB utilized Zenodo to host key project deliverables, publications, and datasets, making them freely available to the public and stakeholders. By leveraging Zenodo, digiNEB ensured that its results were transparently shared, easily citable, and aligned with open science principles. This approach not only increased the project’s visibility but also facilitated knowledge dissemination and reuse within the NEB and digital communities. Through its Zenodo repository, digiNEB has fostered a lasting legacy of accessible resources to support future innovation and collaboration. Access the [Zenodo Community](#) here.

Figure 3 – digiNEB Zenodo Community

Email and Newsletters

A branded newsletter served as a key channel for digiNEB to engage and expand its community of experts across various industries and NEB-related topics. The newsletter provided updates, fostering a deeper connection with stakeholders and encouraging active participation.

Email marketing campaigns were also used strategically to recruit new members for the Early Adopters programme, Thematic Working Group (TWG) discussion groups, and to reduce knowledge gaps by promoting the eLearning courses. Additionally, these campaigns invited stakeholders to showcase digital solutions in the Digital Toolkit and share their adoption stories as success examples.

Newsletters carried the same core messages as the email campaigns, while incorporating engaging graphic elements and images to enhance the visual appeal and impact of the content. This multi-faceted approach ensured that the project’s key messages reached a wide audience and facilitated the continuous growth and interaction within the digiNEB community.

<p>Workshops</p>	<p>A total of 16 workshops were delivered by digiNEB to disseminate digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus, facilitate multi-stakeholder dialogue, and bridge the gap between research and industry. These workshops were designed as "hands-on prototyping sessions," which had a greater impact compared to traditional workshops by focusing on the value creation from NEB digital solutions. They encouraged clustering and convergence on shared themes and challenges, promoted the exchange of best practices, and explored how digital transformation can contribute to the implementation of the NEB initiative.</p> <p>These workshops were central to the project’s communication and dissemination strategy, serving as key platforms for raising awareness and driving participation before the events, and for generating ongoing engagement afterward by leveraging the technical content produced. They created opportunities for the European Advisory Group, Thematic Working Group members, and the broader digiNEB network to exchange ideas and solutions. Workshops were organized in various formats, including face-to-face, hybrid, and fully online.</p> <p>To further enhance engagement, the digiNEB supported these workshops by developing roll-up banners, branded materials, and videos. For hybrid and fully online sessions, additional tools like Mentimeter and Slido were used to increase interaction and participant involvement.</p> <p>A full list of the workshops organized, along with detailed engagement strategies, is available in D4.3 "Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report</p>
<p>Webinars</p>	<p>Throughout the course of the project, a total of 6 webinars were delivered to address commonly perceived barriers and explore how different research and innovation projects are tackling these challenges. These webinars served as online seminars or presentations that helped participants gain a deeper understanding of the goals behind building a digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus.</p> <p>The webinars provided a platform for showcasing digiNEB's assets, featuring members of the European Advisory Group, Early Adopters, and facilitating discussions around the work and results of the Thematic Working Groups. They also played a key role in identifying barriers within the field and discussing innovative approaches to overcoming them. By fostering these conversations, the webinars contributed significantly to the ongoing development of roadmaps and policy recommendations, helping to shape the future of digital solutions within the NEB framework.</p> <p>More detailed information about the engagement strategy developed through the webinars is available in D4.3 "Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report.</p>
<p>Youtube</p>	<p>YouTube is the world’s most popular video-sharing platform with over 2 billion monthly active users. Throughout the project, YouTube served as the primary platform for uploading, storing, and sharing webinars, videos, and other audio-visual materials, ensuring broad accessibility for stakeholders.</p>

This engagement highlighted YouTube’s effectiveness in amplifying the project’s reach, enabling stakeholders to access valuable content and furthering the dissemination of digital solutions related to the New European Bauhaus.

Figure 4 – digiNEB Youtube playlists

Watch digiNEB last video here : <https://youtu.be/pKqNhaCu9dQ>

3rd-party events

Participation in third-party events was crucial in showcasing digiNEB’s main results to external audiences and target groups. These events, organised by entities outside the digiNEB consortium, ranged from international conferences to panel discussions, providing valuable opportunities to increase the project’s visibility, communicate its benefits to target audiences, and gain insights into the latest digital innovations supporting the NEB community. Additionally, these engagements facilitated the development of new contacts and strengthened the digiNEB network.

To ensure impactful presentations, digiNEB partners prepared graphic materials, including PowerPoint presentations, banners, and flyers, tailored to each event. These materials helped effectively convey the project’s achievements and its potential contributions to the NEB ecosystem.

Throughout the project, digiNEB partners actively participated in numerous third-party events, presenting at conferences, joining panel discussions, and contributing to workshops. This broad engagement not only amplified the project’s reach but also positioned digiNEB as a key player in the digital transformation of the New European Bauhaus.

	A comprehensive list of third-party events attended by the team, along with the associated engagement strategies, is available in the Annex .
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Tableau 1 – Communication tools impact

2.4 Value propositions and Communications to stakeholders’ group

digiNEB engaged with seven Stakeholder Groups (SGs), whose main characteristics have been already presented in **D4.3 "Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report**. The SGs have been selected to bring their perspective, expertise, and skills to the project. The digiNEB community has been engaged not only by addressing each of the 7 distinct SGs with the most appropriate value proposition but also through a mission-driven, thematic approach that bridges sectors, ensures interdisciplinarity and allows for self-selection by interest rather than simply targeting specific industries and professions. The SGs were identified to create a comprehensive network to facilitate the connection between the digital ecosystem and the New European Bauhaus. While details about the Engagement Plan for each SG are presented in D4.3 "Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report

Chapter 3 of D5.1 focused on the value propositions tailored to communicate effectively with each stakeholder group. For each SG, the chapter provided a detailed description of how the value propositions are articulated, outlining the messaging conveyed through the communication activities. It also includes an assessment of the overall effectiveness of these strategies, emphasising how each asset will be utilised to encourage the adoption and exploitation of the project results by the respective stakeholder groups.

3. Communication and dissemination activities

Given the strategy described in paragraph 2 and throughout the duration of the project, all project partners contributed to community development and stakeholder engagement on a continuous basis. The dissemination and communication plan included activities that focused on reaching further afield, focussing on the economic, societal and environmental benefits that NEB-related technologies and solutions can bring to society as a whole and potential adopters. The overall communication and dissemination plan aimed to:

- Create an active network which facilitates engagement and cooperation between NEB stakeholders and beyond.
- Analyse innovation in the NEB landscape
- Map NEB-related projects and identification of the assets displayed in the digiNEB website
- Promote digital solutions and services to be adopted by the NEB Early Adopters community in the Digital Toolkit of R&I results and services
- Provide multi-stakeholder engagement and synergy opportunities through events and groups
- Capacity building and best practice sharing

The dissemination and communication strategy were built upon 6 campaigns that run throughout the entire project’s lifetime. The campaigns helped to increase visibility of the project’s results, support its sustainability plan, and support the project’s main goal: increasing the adoption of digital tools for the New European Bauhaus.

3.1 Campaign #1: Branding, Project Communication and Awareness

The aim of this campaign was to establish the digiNEB identity and presence in the New European Bauhaus environment. The campaign started at the launch of the project until the end of the project. The main activities connected to it have been:

- ✓ Branding and rebranding
- ✓ Launch and iterations of the website
- ✓ Set up of social media channels
- ✓ Development of graphic materials
- ✓ Launch of public campaigns
- ✓ Video interviews and promotion
- ✓ Preparation of news pieces, articles and press releases

This campaign was focused on increasing relevant stakeholders’ awareness of the project by communicating, with a consistent visual identity, the project’s key assets, addressed challenges, activities, outputs and expected impacts via project’s communication channels. This campaign was essential to establish digiNEB identity and presence among the New European Bauhaus environment and its stakeholders.

In July 2024 digiNEB underwent a rebranding process to address the limitations of its initial logo, which was a lacked sufficient design refinement. The consortium seized this opportunity to create a more polished and visually impactful logo that better aligns with the core principles of the New European Bauhaus (NEB)—sustainability, aesthetics, and inclusiveness. The updated logo also reflects the project's commitment to effectively engaging its target groups, including policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the general public, ensuring a cohesive and appealing visual identity that resonates with the NEB community. The Table below showcases the main goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders involved in this campaign.

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
October 2022 to September 2023	Develop and refine the visual identity to make the project recognisable as part of the New European Bauhaus community	Development of branding materials (graphic templates, newsletter, roll-up banner, bookmarks) Launch of the digiNEB branded website and iterations Set up and usage of social media channels Press release launch and promotion News pieces and articles about the project’s goals, events on the website and social media channels.	Website visits: Monthly 7K Number of videos recorded: 66 Video recording views: 1985 Communication channels set-up (LinkedIn, Zenodo, YouTube) Social media followers: 1100	All

Tableau 2 – C&D campaign 1 activities and main results

3.2 Campaign #2: Showcasing and sharing digital solutions for NEB

This campaign aimed to showcase digital solutions for the New European Bauhaus, from both technological and social points of view. The campaign was launched in October 2023 and ran until the

end of the project. The main activities connected to this campaign were to launch the NEB digital ecosystem composed of the:

- ✓ Launch and iterations of the NEB Digital Toolkit
- ✓ Launch and iteration of the NEB Observatory
- ✓ Launch and animation of the TWGs
- ✓ Continuous mapping of digital solutions and eLearning courses

Refer to the deliverable D2.1 “digiNEB.eu web platform, Rel. 1.0”.

The start of this campaign was proved by the launch of the Digital Toolkit in October 2022, which was followed by the Observatory in November 2022. The last component of the digital ecosystem has been launched in March 2023 with the eLearning platform.

The main goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders involved in Campaign #2 are showcased in the Table below.

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
October 2022 to December 2024	Showcase the benefits brought by digitalisation in the NEB environment, thanks to the development of the NEB digital ecosystem	<p>Launch of the Digital Toolkit, Observatory and eLearning platform on the digiNEB.eu website</p> <p>Mapping of digital solutions to be displayed in the Digital Toolkit and presented as success stories in the Observatory</p>	<p>Digital solutions added to the Digital Toolkit: 408</p> <p>Podcasts: 13 (available here)</p>	All

Tableau 3 - C&D campaign 2 activities and main results

3.3 Campaign #3: Recruitment to webinars, workshops, annual and 3rd-party events

The campaign aimed to engage various stakeholder groups and raise awareness of digital solutions for the NEB through active involvement and participation in digiNEB events, third-party events, and digiNEB-hosted webinars, workshops, and annual gatherings. Running from October 2022 until the project’s conclusion, the campaign focused on maximising stakeholder participation to enhance understanding and encourage the adoption of digital solutions within the NEB ecosystem.

- ✓ Organisation of 8 webinars
- ✓ Organisation of 16 workshops
- ✓ Organisation of 2 annual events
- ✓ Participation to 3rd-party events

Through these efforts, the digiNEB consortium sought not only to engage stakeholders but also to showcase project results and develop synergies by participating in external events. Given the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) nature of the project, event organisation and participation were central activities from the outset. A detailed plan for these activities was outlined in D4.1 “Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Adoption Monitoring Report 1.0.” and has been updated in D4.3

To bring the campaign to life, the consortium employed strategies, including:

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

- ✓ Seamless registration processes and follow-ups via the project website
- ✓ Tailored social media campaigns featuring banners, branded hashtags, live tweeting/polling, and graphic media cards with speaker images
- ✓ Newsletters and professional multimedia content
- ✓ After event videos, recording of the presentation or availability of the slides

The table below summarises the campaign’s primary goals, activities, results, and targeted stakeholders, illustrating its comprehensive approach to stakeholder engagement and digital solution adoption within the NEB ecosystem.

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
October 2022 to December 2024	Engage various stakeholder groups and raise awareness of digital solutions for the NEB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of 6 webinars Organisation of 16 workshops Organisation of 2 annual events Participation to 3rd-party events Newsletter preparations Promotional materials and banners to promote events Social media activities to promote events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> digiNEB Webinars: 8 Workshops: 30 3rd-party events attendance / presentations: 60 Newsletters: 23 Graphic materials to promote events (both on social media and website): 20+ Availability of recordings of the sessions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEB @CERN - JUST data 	All

Tableau 4 - C&D campaign 3 activities and main results

Example of the participation in Sustainable places: recruiting the research and innovation ecosystem.

The Sustainable Places Conference is a platform for collaboration and innovation, bringing together a diverse network of experts working toward more sustainable environments. This annual event fosters dialogue across disciplines, uniting researchers, urban planners, building designers, technology developers, material manufacturers, utility providers, standardisation bodies, sociologists, economists, and end-users. In 2024, the conference was taking place from 23–25 September at the European Convention Center in Luxembourg. The event focuses on practical solutions and interdisciplinary collaboration to support greener, more resilient communities.

How are the New European Bauhaus Values and Working principles perceived and implemented in ongoing EU-funded R&D projects?

On September 24th, in Luxembourg, Nebula B4P hosted a workshop focused on the New European Bauhaus (NEB) in collaboration with digiNEB and the NEB Academy. The session aimed to raise

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

This brought up the topic of the legacy of historical buildings and evolved to the question of the legacy of new buildings. How will future generations admire the new buildings of today?

The beauty concept can be vague and often subjective compared to sustainable and inclusive. The challenge mentioned is related to adapting new technologies while preserving the cultural heritage, combining functionality aspects with aesthetics providing visually pleasant solutions, and the difficulty of the construction sector and procurement procedures to embrace changes. It was noted that beauty can be a challenge when people are still fighting to survive. Therefore, beauty might be only achieved when no one is left behind.

Value “Inclusive” | Participants shared various strategies for fostering inclusivity in their projects. Key approaches included co-design and co-creation processes, tenant engagement in social housing, and gathering input from diverse stakeholders. Participants emphasized the importance of working in large, collaborative teams, using workshops and tools for stakeholder engagement, and promoting open knowledge sharing. Psychological research, worker training, and involving intermediaries between professionals and residents were also highlighted.

Several challenges were identified in implementing inclusivity in their projects. Key issues included digital inclusion and ensuring broad citizen participation, particularly among different age groups. Managing large information flows, balancing digital and physical engagement, and building trust were highlighted as difficulties. Divergent interests, prejudices, and lack of awareness also posed obstacles, alongside communication gaps between researchers and scientists. Additionally, challenges around participatory foresight and maintaining social trust were discussed.

About the NEB Working principles

Working principle “Transdisciplinary” | Participants agreed that consortia in European projects are more and more interdisciplinary, notably with the increasing integration of social sciences experts. The involvement of local stakeholder groups was clearly identified as a key success factor to ensure transdisciplinary. The concept of citizen science was also discussed.

The main challenge raised by the group was the language issue when dealing with interdisciplinarity, both inside and outside a consortium: indeed, the terms, but also the concepts and values behind them, differ between cultures and disciplines. Reaching a common understanding is an absolute prerequisite to effective co-creation. Also, initiating a co-design process across different pilot sites throughout Europe is challenging, due to different practices and habits of the local stakeholders, each pursuing their own local agenda.

Working principle “Multi-level engagement” | Participants discussed how this was addressed in their projects. They highlighted the integration of top-down and bottom-up approaches, the importance of considering multi-benefit concepts, and the effective use of personal networks. Organizational challenges at different levels were also noted, along with the need for a neutral space where stakeholders at local, regional, and global levels feel empowered to influence project outcomes.

The key issues identified included difficulties in replicating solutions across different levels of stakeholders, split incentives, and balancing mindset changes with organizational shifts. Conflicts arose from differing narratives and dynamic versus static project elements. Additionally, replication challenges were noted, with external inputs varying significantly across local, regional, and global levels, complicating the consistency of project outcomes.

Working principle “Participatory” | Participants discussed that the participatory approach can be achieved through active communication, collaborative research, and knowledge sharing. Participatory activities must be well organised with well-defined tasks for all people involved. Surveys, workshops, presentations, and interviews are tools to deliver this approach.

Excessive consultations, surveys, and interviews voluntarily might be a challenge in the participatory approach. The skillset, training, and political adjustments were also identified as a challenge in this environment.

What did we learn?

This workshop provided valuable insights into how the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles—sustainability, inclusivity, and aesthetics—are being applied in real-world projects. Drawing from the experiences of NEB demonstrators, participants identified both the progress made and the challenges that remain in operationalising these principles effectively.

The importance of local contexts, interdisciplinary collaboration, and participatory approaches was widely emphasised as critical to achieving alignment with NEB objectives. While sustainability is often well-represented, inclusivity and aesthetics were recognised as areas needing more focused integration and tailored strategies. Practical barriers such as funding constraints and the lack of common evaluation metrics were also highlighted, alongside opportunities to enhance stakeholder engagement and drive innovation.

As a key takeaway, participants underscored the need for clearer frameworks and stronger alignment between NEB principles and EU policies to support broader implementation and lasting impact. These insights will inform the next steps in advancing the NEB’s mission and its contribution to a more sustainable, inclusive, and beautiful Europe.

Figure 6 – Discussions on NEB working principles during the Sustainable Places Conference

3.4 Campaign #4: Early Adopters engagement

The goal of this campaign was to recruit digiNEB early adopters and drive the adoption of digital solutions within NEB environments. Launched in M06 and running until the end of the project, the campaign focused on identifying and engaging Early Adopters, stakeholders who actively and positively embrace digital strategies for NEB projects, Smart Communities, or NEB-aligned initiatives.

Key activities include:

- ✓ Set up of a registration form to apply to become an Early Adopter on the digiNEB website
- ✓ Publication of success stories
- ✓ Engage with the early adopters during 3rd party events.

As outlined in D3.1, an Early Adopter differs from a general user by their commitment to championing digital strategies within their networks, providing expert feedback, and contributing knowledge to enhance the systems in use. These individuals act as ambassadors for digiNEB, promoting the adoption of digitalisation in NEB environments while contributing to the project's overall objectives.

In D3.4 Early Adopter network national and regional adoption (final version) are described all the actions led to enhance onboarding of the early adopters and achieve all the relative KPIs. This communication campaign also amplified the digital solutions promoted by Early Adopters through their inclusion as success stories in the Observatory and the Digital Toolkit. The following **notable channels for onboarding stakeholders have been used 1) through the NEB Academy, 2) interaction with the digital and 3) the EU regions.**

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
April 2023 to Dec 2024	Recruit and engage with architects, designers, engineers, researchers, and industrial players that have direct experience using digital tools aligned with the NEB principles.	Organisation of events with the Early Adopters Recruitment of Early Adopters through social media channels, newsletters Early Adopters success stories Early Adopters' solutions in the Digital Toolkit	Number of Early Adopters recruited 149	SG #1, SG #2, SG #3, SG #4

Tableau 5- C&D campaign 4 activities and main results

3.5 Campaign #5: Policy Recommendations

This campaign successfully delivered impactful recommendations to policymakers through a comprehensive landscape and gap analysis reports, and a strategic Roadmap, significantly influencing future work programmes within the NEB and digital environments. Key achievements included:

- Publication of landscape and gap analysis reports, highlighting key opportunities and challenges in NEB-aligned digital solutions
- Development and dissemination of the digiNEB Roadmap, providing a clear strategic vision for advancing digitalisation in NEB contexts
- Organization of a high-level policy event in Brussels, fostering dialogue and collaboration with policymakers and stakeholders

These outputs were developed by the digiNEB team in close collaboration with members of the Thematic Working Groups and the External Advisory Board, ensuring expert-driven and actionable recommendations. The policy recommendations addressed four critical areas:

- Design and Architecture
- Production and Construction
- Community and Sustainability
- Education

The campaign successfully achieved its objectives by equipping policymakers with the insights needed to shape future NEB and digital initiatives. The reported results, including the adoption of recommendations into relevant work programmes and the engagement of key stakeholders at the Brussels policy event, demonstrate the campaign’s effectiveness and lasting impact.

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
April 2023 to September 2024	Develop policy briefs, landscape and gap analysis, and a strategic Roadmap to influence future work programmes in the NEB and digital environments	Recruitment of TWGs through the digiNEB.eu network or through Early Adopters applications Policy recommendations Press Release Digital solutions identified by TWGs added to the Digital Toolkit	Policy briefs produced: 3 Landscape and gap analysis produced by TWGs Release of the digiNEB Roadmap	SG #5, SG #6

Tableau 6 - C&D campaign 5 activities and main results

Example of the Wood4Bauhaus policy event: Onboarding Policy and Wood Industry Stakeholders

At the Wood Policy and Innovation Conference co-hosted by the Wood4Bauhaus Alliance, Bioregions, woodPoP, and Wood Cluster Styria on 7 November 2024 in Brussels, InnovaWood has been the lead coordinator and emphasised in-person engagement to onboard key community leaders and expand the NEB community. This high-profile event highlighted the critical role of the wood sector and industry in driving future competitiveness in housing and addressing the climate crisis. It showcased innovations in wood-based building design and explored how the public sector can champion bio-based construction to combat climate change.

With over 180 participants attending in person, including Members of the European Parliament, EC staff, policymakers, advocacy organisations and industrial leaders, the event provided a unique platform for onboarding a new target group to the NEB movement. Full programme available here.

Why a European Policy Focus on Wood and innovation (digitalisation)?

The European wood sector is a powerhouse of sustainable innovation, contributing 17.5 million jobs, €1,114 billion in turnover, and 7% of the EU’s GDP (FHP 2023). European companies lead globally in sustainable construction, offering versatile solutions for all building types and providing affordable housing and social benefits in both rural and urban areas. To fully unlock this potential, a coordinated European policy approach is essential.

The Role of Wood Innovation in Climate and Urban Transformation

Aligned with the New European Bauhaus principles, wood construction combines aesthetic architectural design, sustainable materials, and inclusive urban renewal. Wood products play a pivotal role in decarbonising the built environment by storing carbon in durable materials like structural elements, furniture, and flooring. By scaling up wood construction, cities can transform into large-scale carbon sinks, turning the construction chain into a carbon pump that extracts greenhouse gases from the atmosphere.

The conference underscored the wood sector's strategic importance for Europe's Clean Industrial Deal, offering practical, scalable solutions to achieve climate neutrality while fostering innovation and economic growth. This in-person event successfully strengthened the NEB community and deepened engagement with policymakers and stakeholders committed to a sustainable future.

Figure 7 – Delegates during the Wood Policy and Innovation Conference

Part I: EU policy perspective | Setting the scene: A competitive European wood sector addressing the future challenges

The conference began with a presentation focused on the European wood sector's role in addressing future challenges. Moderators Uwe Kies, Secretary General of InnovaWood and Chair of Wood4Bauhaus, and Andreja Kutnar, Director of InnoRenew CoE and Professor at the University of Primorska, guided the session. They discussed the sector's capacity to contribute to sustainability, innovation, and competitiveness while responding to evolving societal and environmental needs. This presentation provided a contextual framework for the discussions that followed. The full presentation is available [here](#).

During the opening presentation, Uwe Kies and Andreja Kutnar introduced the New European Bauhaus (NEB) as a central framework guiding innovation and sustainability within the built environment. They outlined how the NEB integrates principles of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity, aligning closely with the values that are followed by the European wood industry. By highlighting examples of NEB-inspired initiatives, they demonstrated how the movement supports the development of sustainable construction practices, fosters collaboration across sectors, and encourages innovative approaches to design and building. This introduction set the tone for the conference, underscoring the importance of aligning the wood sector's future with broader European goals.

Figure 8 - Opening of the conference making reference to the NEB policy.

Part II: Policies and Instrument

In this session, Andreja Kutnar presented on Green Public Procurement and Skills Development: The Case of Slovenia. She explored how Slovenia is incorporating sustainable practices into public procurement, focusing on the role of green criteria in promoting environmentally responsible solutions. She also emphasised the importance of skills development in supporting this transition, showcasing initiatives to equip professionals with the knowledge required for implementing and innovating within green procurement frameworks. Additionally, she introduced the New European Bauhaus Academy (NEBA) hub, highlighting its role in fostering education and collaboration to align sustainability and inclusivity in procurement practices. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

Figure 9 – Policies and instruments panel during the Wood Policy and Innovation conference

Part III : Innovative building products and systems for resource efficient, circular construction

In this presentation, Liselotte De Ligne from University of Gent discussed the new WoodStock Horizon project (grant no. 101181021), which focuses on empowering the climate-smart, circular, and zero-waste use of underutilized wood from both forest resources and the building stock within the construction sector. The project aims to support the New European Bauhaus by promoting the reuse and sustainable management of wood, addressing the challenges of material scarcity and environmental impact. She highlighted how integrating circular economy principles into the construction industry can contribute to sustainable, climate-friendly building practices, aligning with the NEB’s goals of beauty, sustainability, and inclusivity. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

Figure 10 – Woodstock co-creation methodology

Part IV: The New European Bauhaus Academy: Up- and re-skilling the sector’s workforce with innovative training.

Wood Policy and Innovation Conference | Brussels, 7 November 2024 9

Session D
**The New European Bauhaus Academy:
 Up- and re-skilling the sector’s workforce with innovative trainings**

Hosted by Horizon projects **NEBA Alliance** and **digiNEB**
 Session moderator: **Mike Burnard**, University of Primorska & InnoRenew CoE

Time	Title, speaker	
15:30	Architectural education: beautiful, sustainable, together Roberto Cavallo, President European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE), Belgium & TU Delft, Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, NL	pdf vid
	NEB Academy: European Alliance for Innovative Training Hubs Andreja Kutnar, Director/Professor InnoRenew CoE & University of Primorska	pdf vid
	Training of construction workers for the green transition (CoVE Habitable) Višnja Koščak, Manager for Internationalization Holzcluster Steiermark	pdf vid
	The NEB Academy North Hub Camilla Berggren-Tarrodi, Architect and project manager Research Institute of Sweden (RISE)	pdf vid
16:45	Closing of session	

The projects are funded under Horizon Europe.

Figure 11 – NEBAcademy & digiNEB parallel session programme

Architectural education: beautiful, sustainable, together

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

In this presentation, Roberto Cavallo from the European Association for Architectural Education (EAAE) discussed the role of architectural education in shaping the future of sustainable and inclusive design practices. He emphasised the need for architecture schools to integrate sustainability and circular economy principles into their curricula, preparing future architects to address the challenges of climate change, resource scarcity, and social inclusivity. He outlined various initiatives and collaborations aimed at evolving architectural education to align with the goals of the New European Bauhaus, stressing the importance of a holistic approach that combines design, technology, and social responsibility in shaping built environments. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

NEB Academy: European Alliance for Innovative Training Hubs

Andreja Kutnar presented the NEB Academy and highlighted the role of the NEBA Alliance in connecting stakeholders, developing educational resources, and supporting projects that align with NEB principles. By bridging gaps between academia, industry, and policy, the NEBA Alliance aims to accelerate the adoption of sustainable and people-centered practices in architecture and construction. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

Digitalisation is one of the core elements of the NEB Academy, supporting its mission to promote education and collaboration around sustainable, inclusive design and construction practices. The platform will integrate digital educational materials to facilitate learning, project development, and the sharing of best practices among stakeholders. This aligns closely with the objectives of the digiNEB project, which provides a dedicated platform offering digital resources to enable the practical implementation of NEB principles. By leveraging digiNEB's tools, the NEB Academy enhances its capacity to train professionals and foster innovation, bridging the gap between theory and application in the pursuit of the New European Bauhaus vision.

Training of construction workers for the green transition

Višnja Koščak's presentation from Holzcluster Steiermark focused on the HABITABLE project, which integrates New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles into creating sustainable and human-centered living environments. The project emphasises circular economy approaches, the use of bio-based materials, and innovative construction techniques to enhance environmental sustainability while fostering inclusivity and aesthetic value in urban development.

This approach aligns closely with digiNEB's goals of providing digital tools and platforms to support NEB principles. By facilitating collaboration and innovation, digiNEB can help projects like HABITABLE optimize resource use, improve stakeholder engagement, and scale their impact. The synergy between digital solutions and sustainable design underscores the potential of technology to advance NEB goals across Europe. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

The NEB Academy North Hub

The presentation by Camilla Berggren-Tarrodi from RISE focused on the North Hub's role in implementing the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles in the Nordic context. It highlighted how the hub connects stakeholders across disciplines to address regional challenges such as climate adaptation, sustainable design, and inclusivity. Through case studies, the presentation demonstrated practical approaches to applying NEB principles, emphasizing collaboration and the integration of local cultural and environmental perspectives.

This aligns closely with digiNEB's mission of providing digital tools and platforms to support NEB implementation. The North Hub's emphasis on knowledge-sharing and stakeholder engagement mirrors digiNEB's efforts to enable effective collaboration and foster innovation across NEB initiatives. By leveraging digital solutions, digiNEB can further support hubs like the North Hub in scaling their impact and addressing region-specific needs within the broader NEB framework. [Access the full presentation here.](#)

Figure 12 – NEB Academy and digiNEB Stakeholders

Part V : Networking Sessions

The coffee and lunch networking breaks provided a valuable opportunity to delve deeper into the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative. Participants engaged in discussions about its principles and practical applications, sharing insights and exploring collaborative opportunities. These informal exchanges also allowed attendees to address specific questions about the NEB, fostering a clearer understanding of its implementation to drive sustainability, inclusivity, and innovation across the wood sector. Additionally, digiNEB was highlighted as a platform offering multiple digital tools and resources to support the sector in adopting and operationalising NEB principles.

3.6 Campaign #6: Support to exploitation and sustainability

This campaign showcased the project's key impacts achieved through its exploitation activities, ensuring the results contribute to shaping the future of NEB initiatives.

Key activities included:

- Publication of four policy briefs in collaboration with the Thematic Working Groups (TWGs), summarising the project’s main outcomes and actionable insights
- Organisation of events to present the project’s results, fostering stakeholder engagement and leveraging valuable input to help lay the foundation for the next generation of NEB projects

Through these activities, the campaign not only highlighted the tangible benefits of the project but also reinforced its legacy by providing a roadmap for future initiatives within the NEB ecosystem.

Timeline	Goals	Activities	Main results (final)	Groups
April 2024 to September 2024	Communicate the main impact gathered through exploitation activities	Final project’s policy event 1st annual event to showcase the preliminary results of the TWGs landscape and gap analysis reports and of the digiNEB Roadmap 2nd annual event to showcase the results of the TWGs landscape and gap analysis reports and of the digiNEB Roadmap	Four policy briefs and recommendations coming from the TWGs Number of attendees to the annual events: In person 67 (Brussels) In person 55 (CERN)	All

Tableau 7 - C&D campaign 6 activities and main results

3.7 digiNEB Final event & Looking Ahead

Figure 13 – Group picture of final event

As digiNEB concludes and the NEB community reflects on the first generation of New European Bauhaus projects, it’s time to take stock of the journey so far. Over the past three years, significant milestones have been achieved, valuable lessons learned, and the context around us has continued to evolve. Now, the focus shifts to building an even bigger, better, and more impactful New European Bauhaus for the next generation, one that is more mature, structured, and aligned with Europe’s future aspirations.

The December event (digiNEB final event) marked the beginning of a series of engagement activities, designed to reflect on these achievements and pave the way forward. This event forms part of a

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

broader effort to foster collaboration, inspire innovation, and lay the groundwork for the next generation of NEB projects. These events provided a platform to:

- Highlight key successes and insights from NEB initiatives.
- Explore how the NEB context and priorities have evolved over time.
- Host collaborative “Think and Do Tanks” to develop actionable solutions for shaping the NEB of the future.
- Discuss a roadmap for a stronger and more structured NEB, capable of making a lasting impact on Europe’s future.

A full description of content and outcomes of this event is available in Deliverable D4.3: Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report.

New European Bauhaus
beautiful | sustainable | together

NEB | CELEBRATING THE LESSONS LEARNT

A collaboration of DigiNEB with CrAft, NEBULA,
NEB Lighthouses and NEB Labs

17-18 December 2024, Brussels
Architects House

We are wrapping up the first generation of NEB projects, and after the first 3 years we'd like to take stock of what has been achieved. What did we learn? How did the context around us change? And how do we bring all of this now into an even bigger, better, more mature, more structured New European Bauhaus: a more impactful New European Bauhaus for the next generation.

The December and March events are the first in a series of engagement activities, both online and on site, that we hope will contribute to shaping not just the NEB of the future, but also the Europe of the future.

17 December 2024 | ACHIEVEMENTS

09:00	<p>Welcome addresses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frank Van Der Hoeven, TU Delft, digiNEB project coordinator - Annemie Wyckmans, CrAft project coordinator - Jacques Timmerman, Belgian Society of AH, Chair of the ACE New European Bauhaus Work Group - Joint Research Center, Vera Winthagen, Deputy head of Unit New European Bauhaus, Borut Cink, policy officer at New European Bauhaus Unit.
09:20	<p>digiNEB: fostering digital solutions and synergies that boost the New European Bauhaus (NEB) movement Frank Van der Hoeven</p>
09:40	<p>digiNEB results Galvanising the NEB community</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The New European Bauhaus Academy: Up- and re-skilling the sector workforce with innovative trainings Oliver Jancke, InnovaWood - NEB Concepts: Podcast education modules featuring NEB experts on Sustainability, Innovation, and Human-Centred Design in Urban Development Andrew Dubber, Industry Commons Foundation.
10:15	Break
10:45	<p>Implementing the NEB in R&D: Challenges faced by EU projects Clémentine Coujard, NEBULA, Dowel.</p> <p>Think & Do Tank 1 – What have we learned from “learning by doing”? Moderated by: Mia Roth and José Pedro Participation: ALL The power of NEB for effective knowledge transfer and learning</p>
12:30	Lunch
13:15	<p>digiNEB results NEB and the Regions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Opening Statement by Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and Member, EU Committee of the Regions - Statement by Orla Murphy, member of the NEB HLRT <p>The Regional Innovation Model Handbook showcasing best practices from NEB projects Moderator: Andrew Dubber, Industry Commons Foundation.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Kieran McCarthy, Cork City Councillor and Member, EU Committee of the Regions - Eszter Davida, member of the NEB HLRT - Jan Áman, Author of the Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook - Michela Magas, member of the NEB HLRT
14:15	Break
14:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 2 – What have we learnt from EU neighbourhoods? Moderated by: Aase Højlund Nielsen and Annemie Wyckmans with all lighthouses and labs Participation: ALL</p>
16:00	End or networking break

18 December 2024 | WHAT IS NEXT?

09:00	<p>NEB and Digital impacts for industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key digitalisation trends and AI in the NEB – Diana Popa - JUST Data / AI for social good – results from the JUST Data Week, Michela Magas - DigiPedia – Michela Turrin - Wood construction, digitalisation and NEB: the Wood4Bauhaus alliance, Oliver Jancke, InnovaWood
10:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 3 – What is NEB in the digital? Moderated by: Indy Johar and Michela Magas Participation: ALL NEB and digital principles, values, JUST Data, AI, ethical dimension, the line of justice in the digital, AI applications for industry</p>
12:10	<p>The NEB Pocket Guide on Climate-Positive Cities and Communities (CrAFT Cookbook vol.2) Katherine Weir</p>
12:30	Lunch
13:30	<p>Think & Do Tank 4 – NEB legacy: Impacts & Skills Moderated by Annemie Wyckmans and Roberto Cavallo Participation: ALL</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NEB Relay & NEB Alliance - Future pathways for learning and learners (EAAE, Roberto Cavallo)
15:00	<p>Taking results from the NEB legacy into the NEB roadmap: Policy recommendations – ALL projects</p>
15:30	<p>Wrap up – Looking forward: a glimpse into the future Moderated by Frank van der Hoeven, Annemie Wyckmans</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introducing “Shaping Sustainable Futures: Innovating for People-Centric Cities and Communities - NEB Alliance goes forward
16 :00	End of Day 2

Figure 14 – Programme digiNEB final event

digINEB fostering digital solutions and synergies that boost the NEB movement.

Figure 15 – Welcome addresses and digINEB results galvanising the NEB community

digINEB Presentations and Results Showcase at the Final Event

The final event served as a pivotal moment to present digINEB’s key findings and showcase its results to a diverse audience of stakeholders. During the two days were highlighted the project’s tangible contributions to the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem. Through dynamic presentations and interactive sessions, participants explored the practical applications and impact of these tools in advancing digital transformation within NEB contexts.

The presentations were designed to engage attendees, blending compelling visuals, case studies, and data to illustrate the journey and achievements of digINEB. Panel discussions and Q&A sessions provided a platform for in-depth conversations, enabling participants to gain deeper insights and share feedback. By showcasing its results at the final event, digINEB celebrated its accomplishments, inspired future adoption, and paved the way for continued innovation and collaboration in the NEB framework. All presentations are available on the digINEB website.

Collaborative Insights and Planning on the Miro Board

Over the course of two days, participants engaged in an interactive and collaborative process using a Miro board. The initial focus was on identifying and reflecting on lessons learned and key achievements from the project. This foundation then set the stage for discussions about the next steps, enabling participants to brainstorm, prioritise actions, and outline strategies for future initiatives. The Miro board served as a dynamic tool for fostering engagement, capturing diverse perspectives, and driving actionable outcomes.

Figure 16 – Miro board used during the digiNEB final event

Designing the Think and Do Tanks

The Think and Do Tanks were carefully crafted to foster meaningful collaboration and actionable outcomes. Each session was structured to blend critical thinking with practical application, creating a balance between ideation and implementation. To set the stage, the tanks began with a focused introduction to the key topics, supported by data, case studies, and real-world examples relevant to the New European Bauhaus (NEB) ecosystem. Participants were divided into diverse groups to encourage cross-disciplinary dialogue and innovative problem-solving.

Interactive tools, such as Miro boards and live polling, were integrated to facilitate brainstorming, visualization, and consensus-building. Expert moderators guided the discussions, prompting participants to identify challenges, share best practices, and propose tangible solutions. The final segment of each tank focused on action planning, with participants collaboratively outlining next steps, responsibilities, and potential partnerships. These sessions not only stimulated creative thinking but also ensured that the outputs were practical, aligned with NEB goals, and ready for implementation in future projects.

Figure 17 – Think & Do tank 1 presentations

Figure 18 – example of thoughts gathered during the brainstorming session

digiNEB's in the NEB Alliance

At the final event, digiNEB became officially a member of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) Alliance, a strategic network that brings together organizations committed to advancing the NEB's vision of sustainable, inclusive, and aesthetically inspiring environments. This membership will play a crucial role in amplifying digiNEB's impact, and results, allowing the consortium, beyond the project duration, to share its achievements with a broader audience while engaging with other NEB-aligned projects and stakeholders.

Figure 19 – NEB Alliance session

A full description of content and outcomes of this event is available in Deliverable D4.3: Stakeholder engagement plan and adoption monitoring report.

Shaping Sustainable Futures: Building on digiNEB's Legacy

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

Following the success of the digiNEB final event, the "Shaping Sustainable Futures" event is scheduled to take place on March 6-7 in Brussels. This gathering builds on the momentum generated in December, which marked the start of a series of engagement activities aimed at reflecting on the achievements of digiNEB and setting a course for the future. Designed as part of a broader initiative, this event seeks to foster collaboration across disciplines, inspire innovation, and lay a strong foundation for the next generation of New European Bauhaus (NEB) projects. It will serve as a platform to explore transformative ideas and strengthen connections within the NEB community, driving impactful change for a more sustainable and inclusive Europe.

4. Communication & Dissemination KPIs

Description	KPI at M28	KPI objective
F2F General Meetings	5	5
EAG members engaged	17	10
EAG strategic meetings	8	2
Digital solutions mapped and part of the digiNEB Toolkit	509	500
Open licenses (e.g. MIT) with existing projects	50	25
TWGs	4	4
Projects/initiatives in the Observatory	408	250
Policy briefs by TWGs	4	4
Gap & Landscape Analysis report	1	1
Unique visitors to digineb.eu	7K (monthly)	50K (cumulative)
Website Iteration	3	3
Early adopters	149	100
Synergies created	+300	100
Newsletters (sent out)	23	21
Users engaged at events	2000+	2000
Videos	66	24
Social media content items published on socials (Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram)	260	192
Social media followers (total all channels)	1100	7000
Visualisation of videos (cumulative)	1984	120000
Webinars organised (100 attendees each)	6	8
Workshops organised (50 attendees each)	30	16
Yearly events organised (150 attendees each)	3	2
NEB Roadmap	1	1
Attended external events	60	Not set
Marketing Campaigns	6	6

Tableau 8 – C&D KPIs

5. Annexes

5.1 Annex 1: digiNEB events

	Start	Title	Event	Stakeholders		Location	Summary
A – digiNEB Webinar	12/12/2022	Webinar #1 - Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus (NEB)	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders		Online	Webinar with Jan Åman, Duved. This webinar focused on the role of design thinking and user-centred design in empowering citizens and promoting social innovation in local communities. Jan Åman from Duved led the discussion, which emphasised the importance of local engagement in digital transformation.
A – digiNEB Webinar	14/02/2023	Webinar #2 - NEB Digital Talk: How can we register ideas in the creative industries?	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders		Online	Webinar with Sandra Vangadasalam, Bloxberg. A webinar on the topic of digital identity and privacy, featuring Sandra Vangadasalam from Bloxberg. The session explored the potential of blockchain technology to provide secure and decentralised solutions for identity management and data protection, particularly in the context of the New European Bauhaus.
A – digiNEB Webinar	23/05/2023	Webinar #3 - How can timber construction and digitalisation boost the New European Bauhaus?	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	
A – digiNEB Webinar	6/07/2023	Webinar #4 - Harnessing the Potential of Smart Technologies and Local Digital Twins for the New European Bauhaus	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	
A – digiNEB Webinar	9/10/2023	Webinar #5 - Unlocking Energy Efficiency: Digital Solutions for Sustainable Buildings in the New European Bauhaus	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders		Online	
A – digiNEB Webinar	26/06/2024	Webinar #6 - Virtual Reality in Affordable Housing and Neighbourhood Development	Webinar	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Online	
B – digiNEB Workshop	27/02/2023	Workshop #1 - Shaping the NEB Academy lead by the Nordic Carbon Neutral Bauhaus	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Setting the foundations of the NEB Academy	Geneva, CH	Introduction by Ruth Schagemann, President, Architects' Council of Europe (ACE) Moderators: Matti Kuittinen, Senior Ministerial Advisor at the Ministry of the Environment of Finland Helena Bjarnegård, Swedish National Architect, Swedish National Board for Housing, Building and Planning (remotely)
B – digiNEB Workshop	27/02/2023	Workshop #2 - Shaping the NEB Academy lead by Bauhaus Goes South	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Setting the foundations of the NEB Academy	Geneva, CH	Introduction by Oya Atalay Franck, President, European Association of Architectural Education (EAAE) Moderators: Mia Roth-Čerina, Council Member of the European Association for Architectural Education and Vice-Dean for International Relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb José Pedro Sousa, Member of the New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Associate Professor at Faculty of Architecture (FAUP), University Of Porto

B – digiNEB Workshop	28/02/2023	Workshop #3 - Meet the New European Bauhaus Lighthouse projects	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Introducing NEB and digital communities	Geneva, CH	<p>Speakers: Markus Reymann, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice Nicole Arthur Cabrera, Bauhaus of the Seas and TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice Dirk Ahlers, NEB-STAR and Senior Researcher and Project Manager +CityxChange at Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU) Heather Bergsland, NEB-STAR and Project Leader, New European Bauhaus Stavanger Amanda Brandellero, CULTUURCAMPUS and Associate Professor, Erasmus University Rotterdam Martin Luce, NEBourhoods and Director, TUM School of Engineering and Design, Technical University of Munich Aase Højlund Nielsen, DESIRE and Project Manager, BLOXHUB Carlo Battisti, Eyes Hearts Hands and President, Living Future Europe10:30 → 12:30: Third “think and do” session on the NEB Academy</p>
B – digiNEB Workshop	28/02/2023	Workshop #4 - NEB Academy	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Setting the foundations of the NEB Academy	Geneva, CH	<p>Introduction by Michela Magas, NEB@CERN curator, New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table and Advisor to CERN ISAB-g Moderators: Jan Áman, Author Duved and Norrlands Model Florence Kuijl, Communication Manager, InnovaWood Anna Sandak, leader in Wood Modification at the InnoRenew CoE and Associate Professor at University of Primorska</p>
B – digiNEB Workshop	28/02/2023	Workshop #5 - NEB and digital	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Introducing NEB and digital communities	Geneva, CH	<p>Visualising and exploring CERN’s CAD data in 3D, Virtual Reality and Digital Twins Jurgen de Jonghe, CERN During the afternoon the participants will be able to explore the CERN Accelerator and Detector Complex using VR ATTRACT- European platform for breakthrough innovation Speaker: Pablo Garcia Tello, CERN The junction between NEB and digital: Smart Communities Speakers Sandra Vengadasalam (Max Planck Digital Library) and René Ranger (Max Planck Digital Library (MPDL))</p>
B – digiNEB Workshop	28/02/2023	Workshop #6 - Meet the Smart Communities projects	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Introducing NEB and digital communities	Geneva, CH	<p>Facilitator: Davor Meersman (The Maximal Impact Foundation and ICF) Speakers: Tom Minderhoud, Architect and Associate Director, UN Studio Andreas Rudenã, CEO, Paramountric, senior researcher BASAJAUN and digiNEB ICF Anke Schluensen-Rico, The HuT Project and Scientific Coordinator, Climate Service Center Germany (GERICS)</p>
B – digiNEB Workshop	1/03/2023	Workshop #7 - Introducing Beyond Human Ecosystems	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5	Uniting NEB and digital smart communities around missions	Geneva, CH	<p>Facilitator: Markus Reymann, Bauhaus of the Seas and Director, TBA21 Academy, Ocean Space Venice Speakers: Dan Hill, Director, Melbourne School of Design and Professor in Built Environment,</p>

DigiNEB – Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative has received funding from the European Union’s Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL) under Grant Agreement no. 101083743.

				– Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"			Faculty of Architecture, Building and Planning, University of Melbourne Jan Bunge, Director, Squint/Opera and contributor New European Bauhaus High Level Round Table Jan Åman, Author Duved and Norrlands Model, ICF
B – digiNEB Workshop	1/03/2023	Workshop #8 - NEB and digital: the EU Regions and CERN	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Uniting NEB and digital smart communities around missions	Geneva, CH	Facilitator: Michela Magas Speaker: Faezeh Abbasi, CERN
B – digiNEB Workshop	5/07/2023	Workshop #9 - Digital Tools in Assisted Design	CAAD Futures	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Delft, NL	
B – digiNEB Workshop	20/09/2023	Workshop #10 - Digitalization in the built environment	Digital Built Environment: Tools, Projects, and Future Directions in Practice, Research, and Education	"SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG5 – Policy Makers		Zagreb, HR	
B – digiNEB Workshop	20/09/2023	Workshop #11 - Digitalization and education	Digital Built Environment: Tools, Projects, and Future Directions in Practice, Research, and Education	"SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG5 – Policy Makers		Zagreb, HR	
B – digiNEB Workshop	12/04/2024	Workshop #12 - Sharing Experimentation: New European Bauhaus and Digital Interplays - Experiences in Southern Europe	CA2RE Valencia	"SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Valencia, ES	
B – digiNEB Workshop	16/09/2024	Workshop #13 - Deconstructing AI Literacy	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Linköping, SE	
B – digiNEB Workshop	16/09/2024	Workshop #14 - Tug of war: values and security for trustworthy AI	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		Linköping, SE	
B – digiNEB Workshop	28/11/2024	Workshop #15 - Where do we stand with Circular Education?	Circularity in Education	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Delft, NL	

B – digiNEB Workshop	28/11/2024	Workshop #16 - How do we envision our circular education in the future?	Circularity in Education	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Delft, NL	
C – digiNEB Event	27/02/2023	First Early Adopter in-person event	NEB@CERN	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Geneva, CH	(Reported on D3.1) The event ran for 2.5 days starting on the afternoon of Monday 27th February. It combined inspirational talks with 'think and do tanks' – co-creation sessions focusing on the topics that included the new NEB Academy for a sustainable built environment, multidisciplinary Smart Communities, and digitally enabled beyond-human ecosystems. All participants were actively engaged in the co-creation process.
C – digiNEB Event	8/11/2023	First Yearly Event - Digitalising NEB	Barcelona Smart City Expo World Congress			Barcelona, ES	One afternoon event
C – digiNEB Event	16/09/2024	Early Adopter EDIH event with industry	Linköping Science Park	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Linköping	6 day hybrid in-person and online event, colocated with EDIH and JUST Data initiative - full programme in link
C – digiNEB Event	17/12/24	Second Yearly Event	Architects' House Brussels	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Brussels	
C – digiNEB Event	18/12/24	Second yearly event	Architects' House Brussels	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Brussels	
D – Digital Focus Groups		Digital Focus Group #1 Design & Architecture: Parametric design				online	
D – Digital Focus Groups		Digital Focus Group #2 Production & Construction: Bio-based		SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		online	
D – Digital Focus Groups		Digital Focus Group #3 NEB Community: Prize Winners		SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		online	
D – Digital Focus Groups		Digital Focus Group #4 Education training and skills development/ Civic engagement		SG3 – Research & Academia, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG5 – Policy Makers		online	
D – Digital Focus Groups		Digital Focus Group # AI literacy	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		Hybrid	Interactive Hybrid workshop with professionals and practitioners deploying AI systems. Contribution capture Facilitated through interactive online board

1.1 Annex 2: 3rd party events

E – Community events	16/01/2023	Transforming The Built Environment	Transforming The Built Environment			Gothenburg, SE	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	16/02/2022	New European Bauhaus: scaling ideas from the ground up (keynote)	European Union Conference on Artistic Freedom and Cultural and Creative Industries	SG5 – Policy Makers		Umeå, SE	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	6/03/2023		NEBAcademy	SG5 – Policy Makers		Izola, SI	Workshop
E – Community events	15/05/2023		LIGNA 2023			Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	6/10/2022		EC Bioeconomy			Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	12/10/2022	<i>The Role of Regions and Cities in the New European Bauhaus: Regions and cities tell their stories: how to engage communities, develop partnerships and cross-border cooperation within the New European Bauhaus</i>	European Week of Regions and Cities	SG5 – Policy Makers		Brussels, BE	Speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	13/10/2022	New European Bauhaus: Ecosystem Living	NEB Day - Aveiro Week	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Aveiro, PT	Day-long curated programme on NEB Michela Magas, curator/moderator
E – Community events	20/10/2022	Policy Meeting - digiNEB	Meeting with Eric Peters	SG5 – Policy Makers		Delft, NL	
E – Community events	27/10/2023	Enabling spaces for common understanding	Bloxberg Summit 2023	SG3 – Research & Academia		Belgrade, RS	Speech by Michela Magas

E – Community events	3/11/2022	MTF Labs: Feeding Policy Directly from Grassroots Creative Innovation (keynote)	DARIAH Innovation Forum	SG3 – Research & Academia		Dublin, IE	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	2/11/2022		Architectural Education in Times of Uncertainty Symposium	SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Delft, NL	
E – Community events	15/11/2022	Leveraging NEB Communities for Technology Innovation (keynote)	Barcelona Smart City Expo World Congress	SG5 – Policy Makers		Barcelona, ES	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	18/01/2023		OASC Connected Smart and Sustainable Cities and Communities Conference			Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	21/01/2023		Bouwen aan het New European Bauhaus: nu & in de toekomst			Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	23/02/2023		Wood4Bauhaus Alliance GA			Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	9/03/2023		New European Bauhaus projects BK	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia		Delft, NL	
E – Community events	3/04/2023	THIS IS NOT CLAIMABLE ON DIGINEB	NEBA Kick-off			Izola, SI	
E – Community events	20/04/2023		Impact of care; caring for students, for society, for the profession	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Brussels, BE	
E – Community events	28/04/2023		On-boarding to the New European Bauhaus Community			Online	

E – Community events	25/05/2023		Unlocking the power of innovative learning tools for bionic transformation			Online	
E – Community events	25/05/2023	New European Bauhaus Radical Lab 1: Dealing with future human behaviour (lead)	NEB@Venice Biennale	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Venice, IT	Lab run Michela Magas
E – Community events	26/05/2023	NEB as a catalyst of new mind-sets to support the goals of the Green Deal (Moderator)	NEB@Venice Biennale	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Venice, IT	Panel moderated by Michela Magas
E – Community events	26/05/2023	Meeting of the NEB HLRT with President von der Leyen	NEB@Venice Biennale	SG5 – Policy Makers	Positive discussion about NEB collaboration with CERN	Venice, IT	Michela Magas lunch and meeting with the president as part of HLRT
E – Community events	19/06/2023	The potential of culture and creative ecosystems – the bigger picture (keynote)	Perspectives on Cultural and Creative Ecosystems: Partnerships for Impact	SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	5/07/2023	Interconnections: Co-computing beyond boundaries	CAAD Futures			Delft, NL	Speech and panel Michela Magas and Frank van der Hoeven
E – Community events	28/08/2023		EAAE Conference	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals		Münster, DE	
E – Community events	6/09/2023	Tech for radical inclusion: creating spaces for common understanding (keynote)	GoodIT '23: ACM International Conference on Information Technology for Social Good,	SG3 – Research & Academia		Lisbon, PT	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	20/09/2023	Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus	Digitalisation in the Built Environment: Tools, Projects, and Future Directions in Practice,	SG5 – Policy Makers, SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Galvanised regional ecosystem around NEB	Zagreb, HR	Workshop co-organised with Mia Roth-Čerina, digiNEB Advisory Board, NEB Goes South, VP for external relations, Faculty of Architecture, University of Zagreb

			Research, and Education				
E – Community events	21/09/2023	Policy Meeting - NEB developments and future directions	Policy Meeting - NEB developments and future directions	SG5 – Policy Makers	Strategy for NEB, Onboarded national government	Zagreb, HR	Policy meeting with the NEB Head of Unit and Deputy Head of Unit, Croatian Ministry of Culture, and Croatian Society of Architects
E – Community events	22/09/2023	Cross-domain collaboration (keynote)	Climate Security Festival 2023	SG3 – Research & Academia	Galvanised climate security stakeholders around NEB	Helsinki, FI	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	25/09/2023		REBALANCE workshop	SG3 – Research & Academia		Geneva, CH	Followup Workshop to the CERN event in Feb/Mar including CERN, ICT and NEB lighthouses
E – Community events	3/10/2023	New European Bauhaus	Designed Living Environment	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals	Galvanised Nordic city planners around NEB	Stockholm, SE	Keynote speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	11/10/2023	Stimulating Local and Regional New European Bauhaus Grassroots Projects	European Week of the Regions and Cities	SG5 – Policy Makers		Brussels, BE	Speech by Michela Magas
E – Community events	13/10/2023		ItAIS Conference			Turin, IT	
E – Community events	8/11/2023	Congress Session - NEB Alliance: Beautiful and inclusive transitions to resilient, climate-neutral cities and communities, driven by radical collaboration	Barcelona Smart City Expo World Congress			Barcelona, ES	
E – Community events	20/11/2023		NEB-NL -Utrecht			Utrecht, NL	
E – Community events	9/02/2024	Book launch "Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook"	The Local is the Future	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Introduced the Prototype for the Regional Innovation Model	Umeå, SE	The "Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook" was launched at a public event at the Faculty of Architecture at Umeå University on 9th February 2024 entitled "The Local is the Future". The event was introduced by Cornelia Redeker, Head Of Architecture, University of Umeå. The panel included Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, Governor of Västerbotten County and former Swedish Minister of Education; Jan Åman, author of the Norrlands Model and Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook (partner ICF); Michela Magas, Member of the NEB High Level Round Table (partner ICF); Sara Thor, Lecturer in Architecture at Umeå School of Architecture; Adam Davies, Co-Founder of sustainable design agency Tÿ Syml and co-author of

							the “Prototype for an Ecosystemic Handbook”; and Magnus Myrenberg, Partner at Aalto Capital. Speakers included Jan Åman, author Norrlands Model and Prototype of an Ecosystemic Handbook, Helene Hellmark-Knutsson, Governor of Västerbotten County and former Swedish Minister of Education
E – Community events	26/02/2024		CrAFting Tomorrow’s Cities	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		Amsterdam, NL	
E – Community events	23/03/2024		Spatial Capital Automated driving lab	SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders		TUD, NL	
E – Community events	10/04/2024	A New European Bauhaus Economy (moderator)	NEB Festival Forum	SG5 – Policy Makers		Brussels, BE	Panel session moderated by Michela Magas
E – Community events	25/04/2024		REBUILD Congress	SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers		Madrid, ES	Panel session including Mar Muñoz Aparici EAAE
E – Community events	4/06/2024	IS THIS A DIGINEB OR A NEBA EVENT?	NEBA webinar. How to make renovation more inclusive and beautiful? – Renovation projects talk about the New European Bauhaus	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	
E – Community events	11/06/2024		Human freedom in the age of AI	SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	
E – Community events	18/06/2024		The best for the best.	SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers		Barcelona, ES	
E – Community events	20/06/2024		European Data Protection Summit. Rethinking Data in a Democratic Society	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		Brussels, BE	

E – Community events	21/06/2024		Generative AI	SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"		The Hague	
E – Community events	5/07/2024		Digital Sovereignty	SG3 – Research & Academia		Hybrid	
E – Community events	21/08/2024		AI community of practice	SG3 – Research & Academia, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		Online	
E – Community events	2/09/2024		Cloud usage in government	"SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG5 – Policy Makers		The Hague	
E – Community events	3/09/2024	Event #3: Promoting Meaningful Human-AI Interactions: Societal and Legislative Perspectives	Seminar Series on Meaningful Human-AI Interactions for a Digital Society	SG3 – Research & Academia		Online	<p>Speaker: Marc Steen (TNO)</p> <p>Moderators: Stefan Buijsman (TU Delft) and Birna van Riemsdijk (University of Twente)</p> <p>Summary: This seminar explores designing AI systems for meaningful, transparent, and ethical interactions, focusing on societal and legislative perspectives. A framework is introduced to understand AI in its social context, aiming to define meaningful interactions and promote responsible AI through interdisciplinary collaboration.</p>
E – Community events	16/09/2024	Data and technological sovereignty. Bridging digitalisation and security challenges. (TUD) selection of speeches: Collaborative Play, Design to Empower / Empower to Design, Enhancing living environments through data-driven research, Sonification, more than just data, Loud Numbers – Data, sound and social impact, Listening to Data Narratives	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	United technology and industry verticals around NEB principles for the digital	Linköping, SE	Inspirational talks day, see programme link for long list
E – Community events	17/09/2024	Global brainstorming day: Tug of war: values and security for trustworthy AI (TUD), JUST Data collection for training AI agents, Just uses of data in cities	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	United technology and industry verticals around NEB principles for the digital	Linköping, SE	Global brainstorming day, see programme link for long list
E – Community events	18/09/2024	Field trip and prototyping day: Sound for Urban environments, Empowering Artists with Earth Observation Data, Deconstructing AI Literacy, Building a Better Sounding World	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	United technology and industry verticals around NEB principles for the digital	Linköping, SE	Prototyping and workshop day, see programme for long list

E – Community events	19/09/2024	Flattening the world – ontological aspects of data, including the synthetic kind, Sound for Urban environments	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	United health sector technologies around NEB principles for the digital	Linköping, SE	Health Data day, Workshop on synthetic data and prototyping day, see programme link for long list
E – Community events	20/09/2024	AI for social good: JUST living environments. JUST Data Practice – judicious, unbiased, safe and transparent (ICF), AI Act for social good? (ICF) Benevolence and invention, Participatory ethical approaches to the generation of datasets for training AI agents, Launch of the digiNEB Handbook for EU Ecosystemic Regional Innovation	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	United NEB community stakeholders around ethical data and AI	Linköping, SE	Full day programme dedicated to digiNEB 10:00-19:00
E – Community events	21/09/2024	Sound for Urban environments showcase	JUST Industry Data Week LINKÖPING	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders, SG5 – Policy Makers, SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities"	Onboarded regional government to NEB methodologies	Linköping, SE	Results showcase from Sound for Urban environments to regional policy makers
E – Community events	23/09/2024		Conference: Value driven dialogues – Immersive technologies	SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		The Hague	
E – Community events	24/09/2024	New European Bauhaus (NEB): challenging your R&D project against the NEB approach	Sustainable places, Luxembourg	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG2 – Construction Industry & Suppliers, SG3 – Research & Academia, SG5 – Policy Makers, "SG6 – National, Regional and Local Authorities", SG7 – Civil Society & Citizens		Luxembourg, LU	The workshop aims to 1) raise awareness among EU-funded project partners about how they do or could include NEB practices in their R&D approach, and 2) collect feedback on what could be done better or differently to facilitate their adoption of NEB values.
E – Community events	26/09/2024	An EU approach to regulating technologies in the race for strategic technological autonomy	Computing the law, regulating the algorithm: the transformative power of digital ecosystems. I	SG4 – Digital Technology Stakeholders		Madrid, Spain.	
E – Community events	8/10/2024		NEBA meeting Tallinn/EKA Arh Conference	SG1 – NEB Community Professionals, SG3 – Research & Academia		Tallinn, EE	

